

BODY MASS INDEX, PHYSICAL ACTIVITY, AND SELF-ESTEEM AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Body Mass Index, Physical Activity, And Self-Esteem Among Junior High School Students

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Abstract

This research investigated the relationship between Body Mass Index (BMI), physical activity, and self-esteem in junior high school students in Davao City, Region XI, Philippines. A quantitative descriptive correlational design was employed to determine the BMI classifications and physical activity levels in various settings, and dimensions of self-esteem of junior high school. Findings showed that most students have a normal BMI. Physical activity was reported to be moderate. The level of self-esteem was high. While no significant relationship manifested between BMI and self-esteem, a positive correlation was uncovered between physical activity and self-esteem. BMI did not influence self-esteem, however, physical activity influenced self-esteem.

Keywords: *physical education, BMI, physical activity, self-esteem, junior high school, Philippines*

Introduction

Self-esteem among students decreases significantly after they finish middle school but before they enter college (Yan Yan et al., 2021). Self-esteem is how a person rates their value or goodness (Yang et al., 2016). It often drops during the adolescent years (Orth et al., 2015). Those with high self-esteem truly value themselves, while those with low self-esteem may feel unworthy and dislike who they are (Abdel-Khalek, 2016). Moreover, in modern times, many young people face growing mental health problems related to how they see themselves. These challenges include struggles with making friends, acting out aggressively, and feeling unstable because of pressure from peers and bad family ties (Chen & Ma, 2023).

Moreover, according to research, the self-esteem levels of youth in Europe are dropping just like in other parts of the world (Scalas et al., 2021). Self-esteem varies between countries in this part of the world (Delvecchio et al., 2017). To illustrate, Polish teenagers have less self-esteem than Chinese and Italian ones. Additionally, a gender difference in self-esteem is acknowledged by researchers. According to their investigation, Delvecchio et al. (2017) noticed that it is higher for boys of the same age group from different nations such as Poland, Italy, or China than girls at that age. In addition, another study was conducted on Polish students, and they observed a moderate level of self-esteem (Krupa-Kotara et al., 2023). In contrast, in Albania, a study conducted by Hoxhaj et al. (2023), found that most of their participants reported a high level of self-esteem.

In addition, the research conducted in Asia provided more evidence that youth's self-esteem relates to intricate aspects of their life. Research conducted in Bangladesh revealed low self-esteem among students (Dey & Das, 2021). Likewise, in Japan, a study done by Ogihara and Kusumi (2020), showed that the mean level of self-esteem was low for both self-competence and self-liking. Similarly, a study designed by Naeem et al. (2023) in Pakistan revealed that most of the studied population had a low level of self-esteem. However, there were conflicting reports in Indonesia about the level of self-esteem among adolescents. For example, according to Megaputri et al. (2021), teenagers have low self-esteem. Meanwhile, the study that was carried out by Rusuli (2021) recorded a moderately high level of self-esteem. While the research conducted by Hasanah and Tumanggor (2023) revealed that many teenagers have high levels of self-esteem.

Moreover, Garcia and Santiago (2017) conducted a study in the Philippines that showed high self-esteem levels among the participants which supports Dalisay's (2014) findings of people having high self-esteem. Moneva et al.'s (2020) study also discovered moderate self-esteem levels in teenagers. Conversely, another study by Corbita (2023) found that adolescents had low levels of self-esteem.

Meanwhile, in Davao City, a study carried out by Escoton et al. (2023) found a low level of self-esteem among junior high school students. According to their research findings, the participants' self-esteem is so poor that they find it repulsive to look in the mirror. However, a study conducted by Budo (2023) revealed a high level of self-esteem among learners.

Moreover, Body Mass Index (BMI) and Physical Activity (PA) are considered significant factors in determining adolescents' self-esteem (Sani et al., 2016). One study showed a connection between self-esteem and body mass index, where those of normal weight had higher self-esteem as compared with their overweight peers while this was even lower among obese ones (Becerra et al., 2014). Also, it is said that engaging in regular physical activities leads to increased levels of self-esteem (Gilani & Dashipour, 2017). These agreed with Liu's findings (2015) which were backed up by Uchoa's study conducted in the year 2019. However, whether the relationship between BMI, physical activity (PA), and self-esteem is complex in different cultural settings still requires more investigation.

According to Alvani et al. (2016), there was a negative relationship between BMI and self-esteem. Furthermore, a study conducted by Zayed et al. (2016), found a negative correlation between BMI and self-esteem especially in the cases of obesity. Similarly, the study conducted by Krupa-Kotara et al. (2023), also found a negative correlation between BMI and self-esteem. They found that the higher the BMI, the lower the self-esteem. However, in the Philippines, a study conducted by Flore et al. (2017) found a weak positive

correlation between BMI and self-esteem.

In the study conducted by Sani et al. (2016), they found that physical activity was positively correlated with self-esteem. Furthermore, a comparative study conducted by Gilani and Dashipour (2017), found that there is a positive relationship between physical activity and self-esteem. Similarly, a study carried out by Benitez-Sillero et al. (2022) among 1441 Spanish adolescents found a significant relationship between physical activity and self-esteem.

While previous studies have analyzed the relationships between BMI, physical activity, and self-esteem among adolescents, some of which considered self-esteem as a moderator variable while others treated physical activity as a mediator variable; this research is unique because it considers BMI and physical activity to be independent variables that influence self-esteem. Although there has been a significant amount of research on the correlation between BMI, PA, and adolescents' self-esteem, there needs to be more research specifically focused on this topic in Davao City, Philippines. Further, there may be no research on junior high school students in this area, a large population. While research done elsewhere has undoubtedly provided a deep understanding of global perspectives and factors shaping adolescent self-esteem, the challenges and opportunities junior high school students face in Davao City are unique. Thus, this gap in knowledge for a global understanding of adolescent self-esteem for the adolescents of Davao City is the stimulus for this empirical study of the relationship between BMI, PA, and self-esteem of junior high school students in Davao City. This contribution to knowledge will significantly fill the gap and advance understanding among researchers.

The dissemination of this study includes presentations in public forums locally, nationally, and internationally; school learning action cells (SLAC), and journal publications. The findings may also add to the existing pool of knowledge on body mass index, physical activity, and self-esteem among junior high school students, which will be helpful to future researchers in their related research.

Research Objectives

The study investigated the relationship between body mass index, physical activity, and self-esteem among junior high school students in Cluster 13 of Davao City, Region XI, Philippines. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the BMI profile of junior high school students in terms of:
 - 1.1 underweight;
 - 1.2 normal;
 - 1.3 overweight; and
 - 1.4 obese?
2. What is the level of physical activity of the high school students in terms of:
 - 2.1 physical activity during spare time;
 - 2.2 physical activity during physical education (PE) class;
 - 2.3 physical activity at lunch;
 - 2.4 physical activity after school;
 - 2.5 physical activity during evening;
 - 2.6 physical activity during weekends;
 - 2.7 physical activity in the last 7 days; and
 - 2.8 physical activity for each day last week?
3. What is the level of self-esteem of junior high school students in terms of:
 - 3.1 self-competence; and
 - 3.2 self-liking?
4. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 4.1 the body mass index and the self-esteem of junior high school students; and
 - 4.2 physical activity and the self-esteem of junior high school students?
5. Do BMI and physical activity significantly influence self-esteem?

Methodology

This section covers the presentation of the research design, research locale, research respondents, research instruments, data-gathering procedure, statistical tools, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The researcher utilized quantitative research, specifically descriptive correlational design. In quantitative analysis, numerical data are gathered and examined (Bhandari, 2020). Moreover, quantitative research uses the link between variables to test unbiased theories. These variables can be measured to enable statistical analysis of numbered data, often using instruments. An introduction, literature and theory, methodology, results, and commentary make up the predetermined format of the final written report. Those who engage in this form of inquiry assume that deductively testing ideas, building protections against bias, controlling alternative explanations, and being able to generalize and replicate the findings, Creswell (2014).

A descriptive correlational design can be defined as how two variables are related. Using correlations in research serves the primary purpose of identifying connected variables, according to Kowalczyk (2015). Likewise, according to Mustieles (2020), the objective of descriptive correlational design is to describe variables and their association without trying to establish a cause-and-effect link. Correlation studies also describe and predict how variables are naturally correlated. The purpose of measuring correlation is to determine how two or more variables are related and whether there is any correlation between a series of data. Specifically, the researcher examined how body mass index affects self-esteem and the relationship between physical activity and self-esteem among junior high schools in Cluster 13 of Davao City, Region XI, Philippines.

Participants

The study's respondents were 134 public junior high school students in the selected secondary schools of Cluster 13 in the Division of Davao City and were selected through stratified random sampling. According to Simkus (2023), a population is sampled using a technique called stratified random sampling. In this study, it was a group based on grade level which was grade 9 and grade 10.

The researcher utilized the online Raosoft calculator; the sample size was set at a 95 percent confidence level, a 5 percent margin of error, and a 90 percent response distribution based on the known population of the respective schools. The computed total sample distribution of the targeted number of junior high school students as respondents for this study was 134.

The inclusion criteria of the respondents were as follows: they should be officially enrolled students in the selected schools for the school year 2023-2024. They should also be ages 15 and above because it is the age range of the International Physical Activity Questionnaire, one of the instruments that the researcher in this study utilized. The respondents were from Grades 9 to 10 since this grade level comprises students aged 15 and above. Students aged 14 and below in the selected schools were excluded from the study's respondents.

Instruments

The researcher used a questionnaire of three sections: Body Mass Index Questionnaire, which includes the student's sex, birthday, age, height, and weight; International Physical Activity Questionnaire; and Self-esteem.

The respondents' weight and height were measured by the researcher, and the Body Mass Index was computed using the formula (Weight (kg)/Height (m²)). Then, the BMI was classified according to the World Health Organization (WHO) established categories:

BMI	Description
<18.5	Underweight
18.5 – 24.9	Normal
25.0 – 29.9	Overweight
≥30	Obese

The International Physical Activity Questionnaire, used in Peeters et al.'s (1995) study, provided the basis for the questionnaires used in this study. Esto and Poralan (2021) modified the questionnaire format to make it easier to grasp each study indication. The questionnaire underwent reliability and validity tests. Additionally, a pilot test was carried out. Using the 10-item test, Cronbach's alpha of .84 was calculated. All the questionnaire's items were valid and reliable, according to the Cronbach Alpha results, which were within the reliability ranges.

The Physical Activity questionnaire has 10 items and is measured using a 5-point Likert scale: (5) 7 or more times a week; (4) 5 to 6 times a week; (3) 3 to 4 times a week; (2) 1 to 2 times a week; and (1) no physical activity. For the interpretation of the level of physical activity, the researcher used the parameter limits below.

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Physical activity is always demonstrated by junior high school students.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Physical activity is often demonstrated by junior high school students.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Physical activity is sometimes demonstrated by junior high school students.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Physical activity is rarely demonstrated by junior high school students.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Physical activity is not demonstrated by junior high school students.

The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale is the second tool. Participants were asked to rate their replies to 10 questions on a five-point scale between "strongly disagree" and "strongly agree." The RSES is one of the most widely used self-esteem scales (Sinclair et al., 2010). Self-esteem has been broken down into two equally weighted 5-item components, self-competence, and self-liking, because it is not a single notion. The instrument has high internal consistency, test-retest reliability, and predictive validity (Schmitt & Allik, 2005). The high Cronbach rating (M = 0.81) supports the scale's internal coherence. According to Sinclair et al. (2010), the measurement may not accurately reflect trait-based self-esteem. Despite this, test-retest reliability over two weeks produces correlations .85 and .88, demonstrating exceptional stability. The RSES's Guttman scale coefficient of repeatability, which indicates a very high level of internal consistency, is .92.

Each question on the self-esteem questionnaire was rated by the respondents on a 5-point Likert scale, from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The researcher interpreted the self-esteem level using the variety of approaches, explanations, and interpretations provided

below.

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The self-esteem of junior high school students is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The self-esteem of junior high school students is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The self-esteem of junior high school students is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The self-esteem of junior high school students is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The self-esteem of junior high school students is not observed.

The questionnaire underwent reliability and validity tests. Additionally, a pilot test was carried out. Using the 10-item test, Cronbach's alpha of .94 was calculated. All the questionnaire's items were valid and reliable, according to the Cronbach Alpha results, which were within the reliability ranges.

Procedure

Before beginning the study, the researcher sought approval from the Dean of Graduate School at the University of the Immaculate Concepcion (UIC). The UIC-Research Ethics Committee (UIC-REC) office issued the researcher a Certificate of Ethical Clearance. The researcher then requested approval to conduct the study involving junior high school students enrolled in the SY 2023-2024 in writing from the Superintendent of the Schools Division of the Division of Davao City, District Supervisors, and School Principals of the selected junior high school in Cluster 13.

The researcher obtained written informed consent from respondents of legal age to decide voluntarily and those younger than 18 years of age, respectively, with the approval of their parent or guardian. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents following the health protocols as soon as the researcher had permission to conduct the study. The researcher clarified the specifics to assist the respondents in completing the questionnaire. The surveys were returned on the same day they were completed which was examined with the appropriate statistical tools.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that the ethical considerations listed below are met during the research process. So, it is subject to a thorough review by the UIC-REC.

Social Value. The overall goal of the research is to determine the relationship between the body mass index, physical activity, and self-esteem among the junior high school students of cluster 13 in the division of Davao City, Davao Del Sur in the SY 2023- 2024. Moreover, the findings of this study may be used in crafting a needs-based and purposeful plan for the improvement of student's self-esteem and in promoting a healthy active lifestyle.

Informed Consent. The researcher provided an informed consent form (ICF) to the parents of the respondents to orient them with the purpose and social value, the list of procedures, potential risks, and discomforts, as well as its potential benefits. The researcher also emphasized during the recruitment of respondents their right to participate or withdraw, and they were assured of the data privacy and confidentiality before the ICF and assent forms with the signatures of the respondents and their parents before they were submitted back to the researcher as proof of their voluntary participation to be respondents of the study. The ICF and the assent forms were given to the respondents three days before the target schedule of the data collection to give the respondents time to hand over the ICF to their parents. The researcher secured the ICF, and assent forms a day before the data collection. This was a requirement of the researcher before she conducted the survey and submitted honest responses relevant to this study without reflecting their email addresses and personal data to protect their anonymity. Before this, the researcher asked permission to conduct the study from the office of the Public Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, together with the Public School District Supervisor of Cluster 13 then followed by asking the permission of the respective school heads of the participants. By the time the researcher received the consent of the SDS and PSDS, the respective principals' consent, and the participants' consent and willingness to be part of the study, the researcher commenced the data collection process.

Vulnerability of Research Participant. Due to their age, junior high school students were considered a vulnerable group since they were under 18. Their intellectual and emotional abilities were considered limited under Philippine law. Minors legally incompetent to give informed consent had permission from their parents or legal guardians to participate in the study. The questionnaire did not ask for the data of vulnerable research respondents. To ensure that the questionnaire's content does not contain offensive or unpleasant words, it was checked and validated.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. As far as physical harm or discomfort is concerned, the researcher identified minimal or negligible risks. As part of the planning stage, whatever might adversely affect the respondents' relationships, status, privacy, or time were considered to minimize or prevent such adverse effects. For the safety of the participants, the researcher strictly followed IATF (Inter Agency Task Force) rules in collecting and analyzing the data for the study.

Respondents may experience mild inconveniences due to their busy schedules at home and school, which the researcher identified as a possible minimal risk. Personal information such as a respondent's BMI, physical activity, and self-esteem may cause respondents' discomfort. In some cases, respondents might feel too time-consuming and effort-consuming to participate, which results in

nonresponses or dropouts. Answering questions about self-esteem, physical activity, and BMI can cause emotional distress.

To minimize the predictable risks, the researcher prioritized the respondents' privacy and confidentiality, made the data collection process as user-friendly as possible, ensured the questions were neutral and non-judgmental, and provided resources for support and counseling if needed. To ensure that answering the survey questionnaires will not affect their schedules, the researcher planned to gain information on their class schedule and identified the respondent's free time. By calculating their BMI, they can determine if their weight is appropriate for their height. They needed to understand their BMI to identify any health risks they may face. A student's level of physical activity can also be helpful to them. It will be easier for them to achieve their fitness or health goals if they know the intensity of their exercise. The benefit that the respondents had was that they were able to take charge of their health and make positive lifestyle changes because BMI is a crucial indicator of one's health status.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. In the study, the researcher followed Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2018. Anonymity and confidentiality were assured to participants by the researcher. To protect the confidentiality and anonymity of respondents' responses, the researcher did not collect their email addresses or personal data aside from the study instruments' required data.

Justice. In selecting the participants, the researcher used criteria to ensure that they were chosen following the study's objectives. The researcher did not force students to participate in the study. For the tool to be successful, the researcher emphasized the importance of honesty and sincerity. The researcher administered the questionnaire during their free time to respect their time. To ensure the success of this study, the researcher expressed the significance of each respondent's contribution.

Transparency. Respondents were informed fully about the study's purpose before signing the consent and permission form, adhering to the principle of transparency. The findings will be shared with the participants as part of the dissemination plan. The research protocols that the researcher implemented were transparent. To make the results available to participants, researchers will provide a manuscript to the Human Resource Officer and the School Principal. Researchers will also share their findings with stakeholders through meetings, seminars, and forums. Part of the dissemination plan for the researcher is to share the results during the Learning Action Cell or LAC session to increase teachers' understanding and knowledge of curriculum and classroom practices through critical reflection regarding this study.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher earned the required number of units in the Degree of master's in education with a major in Physical Education and passed the comprehensive examination, which is a prerequisite in conducting this study. She has also been exposed to the rigors of conducting quantitative research as a graduate student. The researcher's experience as a Physical Education teacher in a public high school at various levels provided her with the knowledge, skills, and experience required for this study. The technical panel members, UIC-REC, and her thesis adviser was all open to advice, suggestions, and recommendations in pursuing this study. He was an expert in physical activities. He holds a master's degree in education, with a specialization in Physical Education.

Adequacy of Facilities. During this study, the researcher ensured that all the necessary facilities were available and adequate. As a graduate student at the university, the researcher has access to library resources and online materials remotely from ProQuest, e-library, Sage, ERIC, and Gale Databases, which assisted her in reviewing peer-reviewed literature and studies.

Community Involvement. The researcher ensured that the secondary schools participating in Cluster IV participated actively in the study's conduct from the start to its publication. Therefore, she also conceptualized a dissemination plan involving the public, such as a conference or forum, which would involve the public. Other ways to involve the community are to present this paper at local, national, and international research conferences. Educating the public about the outcomes of the researcher's research is considered the researcher's responsibility and obligation as part of the research pool.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data according to the sequence of the statement of the specific questions in Chapter 1.

BMI Profile of Junior High School Students

Table 1 shows the BMI profile of junior high school students in Cluster 13 of Davao City, Region XI, Philippines. It shows that 134 respondents are included in this study. It reveals that more than half of them have normal BMIs (60.4%). Adding on, approximately one-third of them are underweight (34.3%). Meanwhile, the overweight students are 4.5 percent, and the obese students are only 0.7 percent.

This finding means that most junior high school students in Cluster 13, Davao City Region XI, Philippines, have normal BMIs, which means they are within the normal weight range. Furthermore, there were previous investigations where the respondents had normal BMI. For instance, a study done by Zayed et al. (2016) found that Omani adolescents had normal weight. They found out that 55 percent of all participants, irrespective of gender, were of normal weight. Similarly, Davis et al.'s (2019) study revealed that the majority of teenagers (70.9%) among them have a healthy weight. Moreover, there are many underweight students, which may indicate potential deviations caused by poor nutrition, socioeconomic conditions, or health problems (Parra et al., 2021). Overweight and obese

percentages are also low, indicating that this health issue does not particularly plague this group.

This result suggests a high proportion of underweight students in Cluster 13. While a majority have normal BMIs, the presence of underweight students alongside a small percentage of overweight (4.5%) and obese (0.7%) students indicates a potential need for intervention programs focused on healthy eating habits for the entire student population.

The findings are also like Irfan et al. (2019), where the proportion of underweight students was much higher (27.1%) than the percentage of overweight and obese students (10.2% and 3.7%, respectively).

Table 1. BMI Profile of Junior High School Students

		Frequency	Percent (%)
Underweight	(<18.5)	46	34.3
Normal	(18.5-24.9)	81	60.4
Overweight	(25.0-29.9)	6	4.5
Obese	(<30)	1	.7
Total		134	100.0

Level of Physical Activity of the Junior High School Students

Table 2 shows the level of physical activity of the junior high school students having an overall mean of 2.90, which is described as moderate. This means that physical activity is sometimes demonstrated by junior high school students. It implies that the moderate participation level in physical activities could suggest that students do not engage as frequently as they should.

Table 2. Level of Physical Activity of the Junior High School Students

	Mean	SD	Description
Physical Activity during Spare Time			
skipping rope as an exercise		1.89 .95	Low
walking for exercise		3.94 1.18	High
riding a bicycle as a form of exercise		2.19 1.25	Low
jogging or running		2.80 1.30	Moderate
loving aerobics (zumba) as a form of exercise		2.36 1.32	Low
swimming to increase my body strength		2.24 1.32	Low
playing basketball/volleyball together with friends/classmates		2.98 1.53	Moderate
dancing as a form of exercise		3.04 1.41	Moderate
playing badminton as a form of physical activity		2.38 1.24	Low
having played soccer as a form of exercise		1.45 1.00	Very low
Category Mean	2.53	.67	Low
Physical Activity during Physical Education Classes			
<i>In the last 7 days, during physical education classes, how often were they active in...</i>			
playing hard, running, jumping, throwing balls?		3.46 1.05	High
Category Mean	3.46	1.05	High
Normal Activity at Lunch			
<i>In the last 7 days, what did they normally do at lunch besides ...</i>			
eating lunch		2.14 1.05	Low
Category Mean	2.14	1.05	Low
Sports, Dance, or Play Games After School			
<i>In the last 7 days, how many days right after school they have been</i>			
1. doing sports, dance, or play games very actively?		3.04 1.31	Moderate
Category Mean	3.04	1.31	Moderate
Sports, Dance, or Play Games during Evening			
<i>In the last 7 days, how many evenings were they ...</i>			
1. doing sports, dance, or play games very actively?		2.88 1.08	Moderate
Category Mean	2.88	1.08	Moderate
Sports, Dance, or Play Games during last Weekend (Saturday & Sunday)			
<i>On the last weekend, how many times were they...</i>			
1. doing sports, dance, or play games very actively?		3.17 1.16	Moderate
Category Mean	3.17	1.16	Moderate
Describes Them Best for the Last 7 Days			
<i>In the last 7 days, which one best describe them...</i>			
1. doing physical things during their free time?		2.58 1.13	Low
Category Mean	2.58	1.13	Low
Physical Activity for Each Day Last Week.			

For each day last week, how often were they...
doing physical activity like playing sports, games, doing dance, or any other physical activity on:

Monday	2.91	1.19	Moderate
Tuesday	2.84	1.12	Moderate
Wednesday	2.92	1.19	Moderate
Thursday	2.88	1.20	Moderate
Friday	2.99	1.22	Moderate
Saturday	3.52	1.35	High
Sunday	3.40	1.29	High
Category Mean	3.07	.92	Moderate
Overall Mean	2.90	.69	Moderate

In addition, the overall standard deviation is .69 which is less than one denoting that the respondents have ratings clustered around the mean. This finding supports the study of previous researchers such as Chen et al. (2020), and Coşkun and Özer (2018), who admit that junior high school students prefer to be moderately active—in the study by Chen et al. (2020), junior high school students in China believed that they were likely to be active at a moderate level for 3.2 days every week.

Physical Activity during Spare Time. It reveals that its category mean is 2.53 described as very low with mean ratings of the items ranging from 1.45 to 3.94. Consequently, the item having played soccer as a form of exercise has a mean of 1.45 described as very low while the item walking for exercise has a mean rating of 3.94 described as high. This means that respondents engage in low physical activity levels during leisure time. Of the activity options presented, walking for exercise is the most popular choice, while soccer holds the least appeal as a form of leisure activity.

This finding supports the argument of Esto and Poralan (2021), who found that students are less inclined to engage in any physical activity other than sitting around during their spare time. They have no visible participation in physical activities throughout all their free afternoons whatsoever. Students prefer not to do physical activity at all when they cannot make use of time saved from work. However, Oyeyemi et al. (2016) found that adolescents in their study were more active during their spare time.

Physical Activity during Physical Education Classes. It reveals that its category mean is 3.46 described as high with only one item in this category asking in the last 7 days, during physical education classes, how often were they active in playing hard, running, jumping, and throwing balls? This means that oftentimes they actively were playing hard, running, jumping, and throwing balls.

This finding aligns with the study of Smith et al. (2015), which found that, on average, students spent over 40 percent of their PE time in moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA), exceeding recommended guidelines. Furthermore, Hardman et al. (2014) also conducted research that showed that during their PE classes, Chilean secondary students were only involved in low-intensity physical activities. This might be due to the limited time dedicated to PE lessons in secondary schools. On one hand, male participants' level of physical activity during physical education classes was found to be significantly higher than female participants in the study carried out by Doymaz et al. (2024).

Physical Activity at Lunch. As assessed by respondents, it has a category mean of 2.14 with only one item asking the last 7 days what they normally did at lunch which is described as low. This implies that the normal activity of junior high school students at lunch in the last 7 days was standing around or walking around.

This result agrees with Esto and Poralan (2021), which found low student involvement in physical activity during lunch, which aligns with the result. Their findings showed no observed physical activity engagement time, and children prioritized academic programs like remedial courses over physical education or recess. Also, it supports the findings of the study of Whiting et al. (2022), which showed that students in higher grades were more likely to enjoy completing their homework during lunch.

This finding is consistent with earlier research by Saint-Maurice et al. (2018), which showed that both middle and high school students get little exercise during lunch breaks. They observed that adolescents were least active during lunch hours relative to younger children, and during this period, they averaged the lowest duration of moderate to vigorous physical activity.

Physical Activity After School. It has garnered a moderate category mean rating of 3.04 described as moderate. Notably, it has a single item asking the respondents: In the last 7 days, how many days right after school they have been doing sports, dancing, or playing games very actively? This suggests that junior high school students for the last seven days have been doing sports, dancing, or playing games very actively at least two or three times after school. This result suggests that students participate in physical activity to a moderate level.

The research corroborates the study's findings of Esto and Poralan (2021) where physical activity after school hours was only sometimes observed. Their findings suggest that students engage in physical activity to a moderate level. The research findings provide further evidence that recreational sedentarism takes place during periods of inactivity, such as lunch, after-school programs, and the commute to and from school.

This result is consistent with the findings of Mayorga-Vega et al. (2017) in Chile, which indicated that, on average, students spent more

time in After-School Time than in Physical Education classes or during recess.

Physical Activity during Evening. It has shown a category mean rating of 2.88 described as moderate with specifically one item asking: In the last 7 days, how many evenings were they doing sports, dancing, or playing games very actively? This means that for the last seven days, the junior high school students were doing sports, dancing, or playing games very actively at least two or three times during the evenings.

This finding is coherent with documented studies showing that there is moderate-to-vigorous activity by adolescents during the evening, including several hours after Esto & Poralan, (2021); and Brooke (2014).

Physical Activity during last Weekend (Saturday & Sunday). As assessed by respondents, it has a category mean of 3.17 described as moderate with only one item asking in the last 7 days how many times were they doing sports, dancing, or playing games very actively? This implies that during the last weekend (Saturday & Sunday), the junior high school students were doing sports, dancing, or playing games very actively two or three times.

This result is consistent with a recent study (Esto & Poralan, 2021) found that students showed a moderate level of engagement in physical activity at weekends. As a result, occasional observations were made of their activities. The findings suggest that the participants engage in moderate levels of physical activity at weekends. These studies show that while weather and facility accessibility can affect weekend activity levels (Brockman et al., 2011), weekends can still be an active part of the week for many teenagers. Moreover, Weekends have been proposed as a significant target for boosting physical activity because of the greater freedom of lifestyle choices during this time (Hansen et al., 2013).

Describes Them Best for the Last 7 Days. It has garnered a category mean rating of 2.58 described as low. Notably, it has a single item asking the respondents: In the last 7 days, which one best describes them doing physical things during their free time? This suggests that sometimes specifically (1 — 2 times last week), the junior high school students were doing physical things in their free time such as playing sports, running, swimming, bike riding, and doing aerobics.

This result corroborates the study of Esto and Poralan (2021), wherein poor participant involvement throughout the previous seven days indicates that physical activity engagement time was never observed. This suggests that throughout the preceding seven days, the respondents engaged in these few engagement activities. However, a survey by Ploeg et al. (2012) contradicts these findings. Their research with grade five students in Canada showed that daily step counts were significantly higher on school days (when students walk to and from school and participate in physical education classes) than on non-school days (weekends), which suggests that school environments provide more physical activity opportunities than weekends.

Physical Activity for Each Day Last Week. It has shown a category mean rating of 3.07 described as moderate with mean ratings that range from 2.84 to 3.52. It reflects that on a Tuesday, the mean rating for physical activity is 2.84 described as moderate while on a Saturday, the mean rating for physical activity is 3.52 described as high. This means that for the last seven days, the junior high school students were sometimes doing sports, dancing, or playing games very actively for each day last week. Specifically, the junior high school students sometimes were doing physical activity on Tuesday while on Saturday they were often doing physical activity.

The findings support the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's (CDC) recommendation that teenagers engage in moderate-to-intense physical activity for at least 60 minutes daily (CDC, 2003). The difference in activity levels from Tuesday to Saturday can draw attention to the value of unstructured free time for active play and scheduled physical activity, such as organized workouts or sports. Furthermore, Scheers et al. (2012) reports a significant weekly variation in physical activity. However, consistent patterns show a higher level of physical activity throughout the week and a lower level during the weekends. Conversely, weekend behaviors remain essential even though weekday and weekend physical activity levels were similar overall. Weekends have been proposed as a significant target for boosting physical activity because of the greater freedom of lifestyle choices during this time (Hansen et al., 2013).

The Level of Self-esteem of Junior High School Students

Table 3 presents the level of self-esteem of junior high school students

Table 3. *The Level of Self-esteem of Junior High School Students*

	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Self-competence			
being satisfied with themselves in general.	3.60	1.07	High
thinking at times of being pretty good.	3.08	1.10	Moderate
feeling that they have a number of good qualities	3.24	1.00	Moderate
doing things as well as most other people	3.45	1.08	High
having the feeling of much to be proud of.	3.69	1.13	High
Category Mean	3.41	.79	High
Self-liking			
really feeling useful at times	3.40	1.08	High

feeling that they are persons of worth, at least on an equal plane with others	3.21	1.00	Moderate
thinking they have enough respect for themselves	3.71	1.18	High
being inclined to feel that they are not a failure in general	3.25	1.13	Moderate
taking a positive attitude toward themselves.	3.62	1.21	High
Category Mean	3.44	.86	High
Overall Mean	3.42	.76	High

Showing a mean of 3.42 described as high, which means junior high school students' self-esteem is often observed. This indicates that most junior high school students have sound self-esteem.

This result is consistent in the study conducted by Garcia and Santiago (2017) in the Philippines that showed high self-esteem levels among the participants. In their study, out of 66, only 1 or 1.5 percent have low self-esteem and the majority, 65 or 98 percent of adolescents have high self-esteem. However, this result contrasted with the study conducted by Naeem et al. (2023) in Pakistan which revealed that most of the studied population had a low level of self-esteem. The study was done in a school environment to assess adolescents' self-esteem. They also utilized the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES) which measured positive and negative feelings about oneself. Their research found that only a small number of people among those who participated had high self-esteem.

Self-competence. It has garnered a mean rating of 3.41, described as high, having mean ratings that range from 3.08 to 3.69. Notably, the item thinking at times of being pretty good reflects a mean rating of 3.08. Meanwhile, the item having the feeling of much to be proud of shows a mean rating of 3.69. This suggests that although the participants' overall sense of self-competence is positive, there may be room for improvement in some domains of self-esteem (Twenge & Campbell, 2009).

This finding contrasted with the study conducted by Yu et al. (2019), the respondents had a low level of self-competence. The study showed that self-competence, which is the belief in one's abilities, was an important factor in the formation of an adolescent's personality. Likewise, in Japan, a study done by Ogihara and Kusumi (2020), showed that the mean level of self-esteem was low for both self-competence and self-liking.

Self-liking. As assessed by respondents, it has a category mean of 3.44 described as high with mean ratings of 3.21 to 3.71. On the one hand, the item feeling that they are persons of worth, at least on an equal plane with others has a mean rating of 3.21. Meanwhile, the items thinking they have enough respect for themselves reflect a mean of 3.71. Self-liking, as assessed by respondents, has a category mean of 3.44, described as high with mean ratings of 3.21 to 3.71. This finding was in contrast with the previous studies. For instance, a study conducted by Giriraju et al. (2015), found that the respondents had a moderate level of self-liking. However, in Japan, a study done by Ogihara and Kusumi (2020), showed that the mean level of self-esteem was low for both self-competence and self-liking.

Significance of the Relationship of BMI, Physical Activity, and Self-esteem

Table 4 shows that BMI has a negative weak relationship to the self-esteem of junior high school students with an R-value of -0.08. It means that as the BMI of the junior high school students increases, their self-esteem decreases. Also, it reflects a p-value of 0.35, greater than the alpha set at .05 (two-tailed), supports no significant relationship between the BMI and self-esteem of junior high school students. It implies that a student's body mass index is not a reliable indicator of their level of self-esteem. This result is consistent with more complex viewpoints found in other research. Similarly, this finding supports (Alvani et al., 2016) confirming a negative relationship between BMI and self-esteem.

Table 4. *Significance of Relationship of BMI, Physical Activity, and Self-esteem*

	Self-esteem		
	r	p-value	Remarks
BMI	-.08	.35	Not significant
Physical Activity	.18	.03	Significant

It corroborates with the study of Zayed et al. (2016), which found a negative correlation between BMI and self-esteem especially in the cases of obesity. However, the finding of this study contrasted with the study conducted by Flore et al. (2017) found a weak positive correlation between BMI and self-esteem.

However, physical activity reveals a positive weak relationship with self-esteem ($r = .18$) with a p-value of .03 which is less than the level of significance set at .05 level of significance. The statistical analysis of the empirical evidence reveals a significant relationship between physical activity and junior high school students' self-esteem. This means that as the level of physical activity increases, the level of self-esteem significantly increases. It implies that engaging in physical activity can enhance self-esteem in junior high school students. This discovery is consistent with increasing data indicating that engaging in physical activity might enhance self-esteem and overall well-being (Lubans et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2015). Potential causes for this phenomenon include the liberation of endorphins during physical activity, the feeling of mastery attained via physical accomplishments, and the social bonds that can develop through sports and activities (Whiteman, 2017).

Similarly, this finding consisted of the study conducted by Sani et al. (2016), where they found that physical activity was positively

correlated with self-esteem. The higher level of physical activity of the studied population was associated with higher self-esteem. They hypothesized that physical activity would be directly associated with self-esteem, and this hypothesis was confirmed. Furthermore, a comparative study conducted by Gilani and Dashipour (2017), found that there is a positive relationship between physical activity and self-esteem. Their findings revealed that doing regular physical activities was effective in increasing self-esteem.

Significance of the Influence of BMI, and Physical Activity towards Self-esteem

Table 5 shows the results of the multiple regression analysis.

Table 5. *Significance of the Influence of BMI, and Physical Activity towards Self-esteem*

Singular Influence of the Predictors	Standardized Coefficients	Self-esteem		Remarks
		t	p-value	
BMI	.09	-1.05	.30	Not Significant
Physical Activity	.19	2.20	.03	Significant
Combined Influence of the Predictors				
R	.20			
R ²	.04			
F	2.87			
p	.06			Not Significant

In singular capacity, the BMI shows a p-value of .30 which is greater than the .05 level of significance (2-tailed) with a negative standardized beta value of -1.05. It means that for every unit increase in the value of the level of BMI, there is a corresponding decrease of 1.05 in the level of self-esteem. However, the influence of BMI on self-esteem is not significant.

Likewise, the independent variable, physical activity reflects a p-value of .03 which is less than the .05 level of significance (2-tailed) with a positive standardized beta value of .19. It means that in singular capacity, physical activity is a significant predictor of the level of self-esteem wherein for every unit increase in the level of physical activity there is a corresponding increase of .19 in the level of self-esteem.

In addition, the combined influence of the two independent variables, BMI, and physical activity towards self-esteem is not significant with a p-value of 0.06 which is greater than the .05 level of significance (2-tailed) ($F = 2.87$). Meanwhile, the model explains four percent of the variance of self-esteem of junior high school students based on the independent variables included in this study as indicated by $R^2 = .04$. This means that 96 percent of the variance in self-esteem can be attributed to other factors aside from BMI, and physical activity.

This finding is partially consistent with expectations, as physical activity significantly positively influences self-esteem, while BMI did not have a statistically significant effect. While physical activity emerged as a significant positive predictor of self-esteem ($\beta = .19$, $p = .03$), BMI did not exert a statistically significant influence ($\beta = -1.05$, $p = .30$).

Moreover, these results align with research by Dey et al. (2021). According to their study, the statistical analysis revealed no significant relationship between BMI and self-esteem. However, this was in contrast with the study conducted by Zayed et al. (2016), where they emphasized the potential influence of BMI on the self-esteem of adolescents. On one hand, a study carried out by Benitez-Sillero et al. (2022) among 1441 Spanish adolescents found a significant relationship between physical activity and self-esteem. This supports the findings that physical activity is a significant predictor of the level of self-esteem.

Furthermore, the combined influence of BMI and physical activity on self-esteem was not statistically significant ($p = .06$). This suggests potentially more complex interactions between these variables, influenced by factors like gender, as observed by Vedøy et al. (2021) Their cross-sectional study indicated that girls with higher BMI might experience lower self-esteem compared to boys, with physical activity having a more substantial positive effect on self-esteem in girls (Vedøy et al., 2021)

The low explanatory power of the model ($R^2 = .04$) underscores the need for further investigation into additional factors influencing self-esteem in junior high school students. Future research could explore the roles of social support networks, academic performance, and the internalization of media-driven body image ideals (Aparicio-Martínez et al., 2019)

Finally, the study's results show a connection between body mass index (BMI) exercise and self-esteem in junior high school students explained using Rosenberg's Self Esteem Theory. Even though there is a link between BMI and self-esteem, the lack of a significant relationship suggests that other factors have a more significant impact.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that: (1) Most junior high school students in Cluster 13, Davao City Region XI, Philippines, have normal BMIs, which means they were within the normal weight range. Moreover, there were many underweight students. Overweight and obese percentages were also low. (2) Physical activity was sometimes demonstrated by junior high school students. This was observed after school, during the evening, during weekends, and for each day last week. (3) The self-esteem of junior high

school students was often observed. This result connotes students' self-esteem is high in terms of self-competence and self-liking. (4) There was no significant relationship between BMI and self-esteem in the junior high school student population studied. However, the level of physical activity increases the level of self-esteem significantly, which means that encouraging regular physical activity could be a valuable strategy for promoting positive self-esteem among junior high school students. (5) The combined influence of Body Mass Index and physical activity did not significantly influence the level of self-esteem BMI did not significantly influence self-esteem; however, physical activity significantly influenced self-esteem. This implies that, while BMI was not a major determinant of self-esteem in this population, however, a physical activity played a beneficial role.

Moreover, the following were recommended based on the findings of the study: (1) Considering that there are normal-weight and underweight students in Cluster 13, it is necessary to have a comprehensive school-based nutrition program. This will be geared towards informing adolescents about healthy eating habits and the need to keep down their intake of food as well as consume a balanced diet for their general health and well-being. To cater to the diverse nutritional needs of all these students, the underweight students will get specific advice on healthy weight gain techniques. The program intends to involve school administrators, teachers, parents, and nutritionists to form an atmosphere encouraging good eating habits which will include them reaching a healthy weight. (2) Cluster 13 middle schools should adopt a holistic approach to address the irregular physical activity levels observed among students, despite having mandatory Physical Education (PE) classes. This entails doing any or all the following—improving on the available PE program to ensure at least 60 minutes of moderate-to-vigorous activity each day by transforming it into more interesting and varied activities, lengthening teaching sessions or increasing their intensity—and creating opportunities for movement across the curriculum through collaboration with other teachers within the school. Also, administrators within the school system as well as PE teachers and coaches will join hands with parents to organize “After-school” programs such as sports games, and fitness activities and encourage parents to have their children walk or cycle to and from school. The schools can do this by integrating sporting clubs and active commuting campaigns into their structures. To engender a culture of wellness among Cluster 13's junior high school students, they must have adequate physical activity for both mental and bodily development purposes. (3) While most of the students exhibit very high self-esteem, it is important that this positive aspect of their lives be sustained and improved regularly. Therefore, it is recommended that a school-wide self-esteem enhancement program may be established which will focus on building self-confidence, self-efficacy, and positive body image. This program seeks to make students more aware of themselves, set goals for themselves, and engage in positive thinking about themselves as well as offer them extracurricular activities to give them tools for their teenage years and beyond so that they can maintain a healthy level of self-esteem in the future. (4) This study did not find any significant relationship between BMI and self-esteem, but a positive correlation was also observed between physical activity and self-esteem. To follow up on this finding, the researchers should collaborate with school administrators to investigate how various factors, which are highly complex in nature, impacts on the self-esteem of junior high school pupils. This research should look deeper into the connection that exists between BMI and self-esteem by looking at other variables such as body image dissatisfaction, social comparison, and peer pressure. In addition to this, schools can encourage self-esteem through physical activities programs because it is one main factor that enhances students' love for themselves. Such activities may encompass provision of an enabling environment for those who elect to participate in different kinds of sports besides recognizing awards won by students as incentives that demonstrate the positive link amid exercises and self-esteem. A multifaceted approach will assist in developing more targeted interventions that address multiple factors affecting adolescents' esteem thus improving their general wellbeing. (5) The study observed a very strong association between self-esteem and physical activity. It has been highly recommended that schools may create an environment that highly appreciates physical activities because of this. This means providing a broad selection of physical activities to suit different tastes and capabilities, which guarantees that all students can find interesting ways to engage in exercise. Again, by honoring and acknowledging student accomplishments in sporting activities, it will also help continue to strengthen the connection between getting involved in physical fitness programs with self-image leading to a sense of fulfillment or acknowledgment and pride which contributes positively towards their living at large. (6) Future research may investigate other variables that may improve the self-esteem of junior high school students. For future studies involving Asian participants, it is recommended to consider employing the Asian Standard or Asia-Pacific BMI classifications. These classifications are tailored to the unique body composition of Asian individuals and may provide a more accurate assessment of health risks associated with body weight compared to the standard BMI classification. (7) To further refine the findings, it is recommended that future research in this area may stratify participants by gender. This approach would account for the known differences in body composition between males and females and may yield more precise insights into the relationship between BMI and health outcomes.

References

- Abdel-Khalek, A. M. (2016). Introduction to the psychology of self-esteem. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311440256_Introduction_to_the_Psychology_of_self-esteem
- Ahadzadeh, A. S., Rafik-Galea, S., Alavi, M., & Amini, M. (2018). Relationship between body mass index, body image, and fear of negative evaluation: Moderating role of self-esteem. *Health Psychology Open*, 5(1), 205510291877425. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055102918774251>
- Alkhateeb, S. A., Alkhameesi, N. F., Lamfon, G. N., Khawandanh, S. Z., Kurdi, L. K., Faran, M. Y., Khoja, A. A., Bukhari, L. M., Aljhdali, H. R., Ashour, N. A., Bagasi, H. T., Delli, R. A., Khoja, O. A., & Safdar, O. Y. (2019). Pattern of physical exercise practice among university students in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (before beginning and during college): A cross-sectional study. *BMC Public*

Health, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-8093-2>

Alvani, S. R., Mehrshad, S., Hosseini, P., & Kimura, L. W. (2016). Relationship between Body Weight and Self-Esteem: A Study of Young Men and Women in Iran. *Journal of Obesity and Overweight*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.15744/2455-7633.2.202>

Angeles-Agdeppa, I., Lenighan, Y. M., Jacquier, E., Toledo, M. B., & Capanzana, M. (2019). The impact of wealth status on food intake patterns in Filipino School-Aged children and Adolescents. *Nutrients*, 11(12), 2910. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11122910>

Aparicio-Martínez, P., Perea-Moreno, A., Redel-Macías, M. D., Pagliari, C., & Vaquero-Abellán, M. (2019). Social Media, Thin-Ideal, Body Dissatisfaction and Disordered Eating Attitudes: An Exploratory analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(21), 4177. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16214177>

Arriscado, D., Muros, J., Zabala, M., & Dalmau, J. (2015). Influencia del sexo y el tipo de escuela sobre los indices de sobrepeso y obesidad. *Rev Pediatr Aten Primaria*.

Arundell, L., Ridgers, N. D., Veitch, J., Salmon, J., Hinkley, T., & Timperio, A. (2013). 5-Year changes in Afterschool physical activity and sedentary behavior. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 44(6), 605-611. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2013.01.029>

Becerra, M. O., Muros, J. J., Cuadros, J. P., Sánchez, J. M., & González, M. C. (2015). Influence of BMI on self-esteem of children aged 12–14 years. *Anales De Pediatría*, 83(5), 311–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anpede.2014.11.003>

Benazeera, U. J. C. (2014). Association between eating habits and body mass index (BMI) of adolescents. *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*, 3(8), 940–943. <https://www.ejmanager.com/mnstemps/67/67-1398682622.pdf>

Bhandari, P. (2020). An introduction to quantitative research. www.scribbr.com. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>

Brockman, R., Jago, R., & Fox, K. R. (2011). Children’s active play: self-reported motivators, barriers, and facilitators. *BMC Public Health*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-11-461>

Brooke, H. L., Corder, K., Atkin, A. J., & Van Sluijs, E. M. (2014). A systematic literature review with meta-analyses of within- and between-day differences in objectively measured physical activity in school-aged children. *Sports Medicine*, 44(10), 1427-1438. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-014-0215-5>

Brown, C. L., Gibbons, L. E., Kennison, R. F., Robitaille, A., Lindwall, M., Mitchell, M. B., Shirk, S. D., Atri, A., Cimino, C. R., Benitez, A., MacDonald, S. W., Zelinski, E. M., Willis, S. L., Schaie, K. W., Johansson, B., Dixon, R. A., Mungas, D. M., Hofer, S. M., & Piccinin, A. M. (2012). Social activity and cognitive functioning over time: A coordinated analysis of four longitudinal studies. *Journal of Aging Research*, 2012, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/287438>

Budo, C. (2023). School quality and self-esteem of Compostela National High School [MA Thesis]. University of Mindanao, Tagum City.

Bulbul, T., & Hoque, M. (2014). Prevalence of childhood obesity and overweight in Bangladesh: findings from a countrywide epidemiological study. *BMC Pediatrics*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2431-14-86>

Camacho, S., & Ruppel, A. (2017). Is the calorie concept a real solution to the obesity epidemic? *Global Health Action/Global Health Action. Supplement*, 10(1), 1289650. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16549716.2017.1289650>

Catequista, I., & Uy, G. (2013). Relationships of healthy lifestyle determinants among private high school students in Iloilo City, Philippines. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(10).

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. CDC overweight & obesity. (2022). <https://www.cdc.gov/obesity/index.html>

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2014). *Comprehensive School Physical Activity Programs: A Guide for Schools*. Department of Health and Human Services: Atlanta, GA, USA.

Chen, N., Zhou, M., Dong, X., Qu, J., Gong, F., Han, Y., Qiu, Y., Wang, J., Liu, Y., Yuan, W., Xia, J., Takata, Y., Zhang, X., & Zhang, L. (2020). Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of 99 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a descriptive study. *Lancet*, 395(10223), 507–513. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(20\)30211-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(20)30211-7)

Chen, X., & Ma, R. (2023). Adolescents’ Self-Esteem: The Influence Factors and Solutions. *Journal of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 8, 1562-1566. <https://doi.org/10.54097/ehss.v8i.4520>

Corbita, A. (2023). Self-Esteem And Adversity Quotient Among Senior High School Learners, Clarin District, Bohol. *Peak Learning*. <https://www.peaklearning.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/ANALYN-CORBITA.pdf>

Coşkun, A., & Özer, M. K. (2018). COMPARISON OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY LEVELS OF MIDDLE SCHOOL AND HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sports Science*, 4(8). <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejep/article/view/1752>

Creswell, J. W. (2014). *A concise introduction to mixed methods research*. SAGE Publications.

Dalisay, M. (2014). Parenting Styles and Self-Esteem among Criminology students of Lyceum of the Philippines University-Batangas City. *Graduate School Research Journal*, 7(2).

Davis, L., Barnes, A. J., Gross, A. C., Ryder, J. R., & Schlafer, R. J. (2019). Adverse Childhood Experiences and Weight Status among Adolescents. *the Journal of Pediatrics/the Journal of Pediatrics*, 204, 71-76.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2018.08.071>

Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in human behavior. In Springer eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-2271-7>

Delvecchio, E., Liberska, H., Lis, A., & Li, J. B. (2017). The level of self-esteem among Polish adolescents in a cross-cultural context. *Polskie Forum Psychologiczne*, 22(2), 189-204. DOI: 10.14656/PFP20170201

Department of Education. (2016). K to 12 Curriculum Guide Physical Education. <http://depedbohol.org/v2/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/PE-CG.pdf> (accessed October 5, 2020)

Dey, T., Rifat, N., & Das, A. (2021). Influence of body mass index on self-esteem among school adolescents. *Jalalabad Medical Journal*, 18(1), 11–17.

De Dios Benitez-Sillero, J., Portela-Pino, I., Morente, Á., & Raya-González, J. (2023). Longitudinal relationships between physical fitness with physical Self-Concept and Self-Esteem in adolescents. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2023.2173134>

Don, S., Layosa, M., Evangelista, G., & Atienza, L. (2020). Perceived Nutritional Status, Body Satisfaction and Fad Dieting among Middle-Adolescent Students of the University of the Philippines Rural High School. www.academia.edu. https://www.academia.edu/110196290/Perceived_Nutritional_Status_Body_Satisfaction_and_Fad_Dieting_among_Middle_Adolescent_Students_of_the_University_of_the_Philippines_Rural_High_School

Donnellan, M. B., Trzesniewski, K. H., Robins, R. W., Moffitt, T. E., & Caspi, A. (2015). Low Self-Esteem is related to aggression, antisocial behavior, and delinquency. *Psychological Science*, 16(4), 328–335. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0956-7976.2005.01535.x>

Doymaz, F., Çakir Topukçu, Ö., ATalay, O., Özkeskin, M., & Şenol, H. (2024). The relationship between physical activity and self-esteem among Turkish university students: A gender perspective; a multidisciplinary and multi-center study. *Anatolian Current Medical Journal*, 6(1), 17-22. <https://doi.org/10.38053/acmj.1343019>

Drenowatz, C., Gribben, N., Wirth, M. D., Hand, G. A., Shook, R. P., Burgess, S., & Blair, S. N. (2016). The association of physical activity during weekdays and weekend with body composition in young adults. *Journal of Obesity*, 2016, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/8236439>

Dubieliš, A. (2021). Physical Activity and Self-esteem of Young People on the Example of Secondary School Students from Lublin. *Annales Universitatis Mariae Curie-Skłodowska. Section J, Paedagogia-Psychologia*, 34(1), 207. <https://doi.org/10.17951/j.2021.34.1.207-220>

D'Isanto, T. (2016). Pedagogical value of the body and physical activity in childhood. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311390164_Pedagogical_value_of_the_body_and_physical_activity_in_childhood

Escoton, F. H., Baliad, J., & Galabo, N. R. (2023). The Unspoken Emotions: The Body Shaming Experiences of Senior High School Students. *Research Gate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373839131_The_Unspoken_Emotions_The_Body_Shaming_Experiences_of_Senior_High_School_Students

Esto, J. B., & Poralan, P. S. (2021). Understanding personality traits of students and their physical activity engagement: A convergent design. *International Journal of Physical education, Sports, and Health*, 8(4), 342-354. <https://doi.org/10.22271/kheljournal.2021.v8.i4f.2203>

Evenson, K. R., Wen, F., Metzger, J. S., & Herring, A. H. (2015). Physical activity and sedentary behavior patterns using accelerometry from a national sample of United States adults. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-015-0183-7>

Fairclough, S. J., Boddy, L. M., Mackintosh, K. A., Valencia-Peris, A., & Ramirez-Rico, E. (2015). Weekday and weekend sedentary time and physical activity in differentially active children. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 18(4), 444-449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2014.06.005>

- Fairclough, S., & Stratton, G. (2005). undefined. *Pediatric Exercise Science*, 17(3), 217-236. <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.17.3.217>
- Flores, J., Fragante, J., Francisco, J., Dipasupil, J., Damaso, P., Gutierrez, Dela Guerra, K. K., Escudero, M., Estella, R. A., Evasco, M. K., Galang, S. G., Humarang, J., Villavicencio, & Sison, R. (2016). The correlation between body mass index and self-esteem among children ages 9-12 years old in a public elementary school in Makati City, Philippines. *Pediatrics and Primary Care Physicians (PPCP)*.
- Garcia, Q., & Santiago, A. B. (2017). Parenting styles as correlates to self-esteem of underprivileged adolescents: basis for a proposed parenting skills program. *International Journal of Advanced Education and Research*, 2(5), 27–35.
- Gilani, S. R. M., & Dashipour, A. (2016). The Effects of Physical activity on Self-Esteem: A Comparative study. *International Journal of High Risk Behaviors and Addiction*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.5812/ijhrba.35955>
- Giles, L. V., Koehle, M. S., Saelens, B. E., Sbihi, H., & Carlsten, C. (2021). When physical activity meets the physical environment: precision health insights from the intersection. *Environmental Health and Preventive Medicine*, 26(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12199-021-00990-w>
- Giriraju, A., & Lakshminarayan, N. (2015). Relationship of self-liking, self-competence with self-reported oral health status among 15-year-old children of Davangere city: A cross-sectional survey. *Journal of the Indian Association of Public Health Dentistry/Journal of Indian Association of Public Health Dentistry*, 13(4), 417. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2319-5932.171175>
- Grao-Cruces, A., Velásquez-Romero, M. J., & Rodriguez-Rodríguez, F. (2020). Levels of Physical Activity during School Hours in Children and Adolescents: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(13), 4773. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134773>
- Gurung, T. R., & VI, N. G. (2014, June 1). Overweight and Obesity among the Adolescent School Students in Belgaum City. *PubMed*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26905706/>
- Hansen, B. H., Holme, I., Anderssen, S. A., & Kolle, E. (2013). Patterns of objectively measured physical activity in normal weight, overweight, and obese individuals (20–85 years): A cross-sectional study. *PLoS ONE*, 8(1), e53044. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0053044>
- Hardman, K., Murphy, C., Routen, A., & Tones, S. (2014). World-wide survey of school physical education: final report. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- Hasanah, R., & Tumanggor, R. (2023). The relationship of self-esteem to narcissistic in teenagers using TikTok social media during the COVid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Application on Social Science and Humanities*, 1(1), 727–735. <https://doi.org/10.24912/ijassh.v1i1.25938>
- Hoxhaj, B., Khani, D., Kapo, S., & Sinaj, E. (2023). The role of social media on Self-Image and Self-Esteem: A study on Albanian teenagers. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 13(4), 128. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2023-0096>
- Inokuchi, M., Matsuo, N., Takayama, J. I., & Hasegawa, T. (2014). Trends in thin body stature among Japanese male adolescents, 2003–2012. *Annals of Human Biology*, 41(3), 277–281. <https://doi.org/10.3109/03014460.2013.856938>
- Inokuchi, M., Matsuo, N., Takayama, J. I., & Hasegawa, T. (2015). Trends in thin body stature among Japanese female adolescents, 2003–2012. *Annals of Human Biology*, 42(6), 533–537. <https://doi.org/10.3109/03014460.2014.975280>
- Ibrahim, S., Akram, Z., Noreen, A., Baig, M. T., Sheikh, S., Huma, A., Jabeen, A., Lodhi, M., Khan, S. A., Hudda, A., Shahid, U., & Syed, N. (2021). Overweight and obesity prevalence and predictors in people living in Karachi. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, 194–202. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jpri/2021/v33i31b31708>
- Irfan, M., Jabbar, M., & Hameed, S. (2019). Dietary Habits and Prevalence of Underweight/ Obesity in Students of University of Gujrat, Pakistan. *Journal of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences*, 18(02), 175-180. <https://doi.org/10.22442/jlumhs.191820623>
- Javed, A., Jumeen, M., Murad, M. H., Okorodudu, D., Kumar, S., Somers, V., Sochor, O., & Lopez-Jimenez, F. (2014). Diagnostic performance of body mass index to identify obesity as defined by body adiposity in children and adolescents: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Pediatric Obesity*, 10(3), 234–244. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijpo.242>
- Kantanista, A., & Osiński, W. (2014). Underweight in 14 to 16 year-old girls and boys: Prevalence and associations with physical activity and sedentary activities. *PubMed*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24738508/>
- Karimi, A., & Saadatmand, Z. (2014). The Relationship between Self-Confidence with Achievement Based on Academic Motivation. *Deleted Journal*, 4(1), 210–215. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0018904>
- Khan, M., Khan, I., Jan, F., Khan, S., & Saif, N. (2015). The Self-Esteem: A Review of Literature. *International Journal of African and*

Asian Studies, 9.

Kircaburun, K., & Griffiths, M. D. (2018). Instagram addiction and the Big Five of personality: The mediating role of self-liking. *Journal of Behavioral Addictions*, 7(1), 158–170. <https://doi.org/10.1556/2006.7.2018.15>

Kowalczyk, D. (2015). Descriptive Research, Design, Definition, Examples, Type. Study.com. <http://study.com/academy/lesson/>.

Krupa-Kotara, K., Markowski, J., Gdańska, A., Grajek, M., Działach, E., Szlachta, G., & Rozmiarek, M. (2023). Global self-esteem, body composition, and physical activity in Polish University students. *Nutrients*, 15(18), 3907. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15183907>

Lau, E. Y., Dowda, M., McIver, K. L., & Pate, R. R. (2017). Changes in physical activity in the school, Afterschool, and evening periods during the transition from elementary to middle school. *Journal of School Health*, 87(7), 531-537. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.12523>

Lawrence, E., Mollborn, S., & Hummer, R. A. (2017). Health lifestyles across the transition to adulthood: Implications for health. *Social Science & Medicine*, 193, 23–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2017.09.041>

Leavitt, P., Covarrubias, R., Perez, Y., & Fryberg, S. (2015). “Frozen in Time”: The Impact of Native American Media representations on Identity and Self-Understanding. *Journal of Social Issues*, 71(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/josi.12095>

Liu, M., Wu, L., & Ming, Q. (2015). How does physical activity intervention improve self-esteem and self-concept in children and adolescents? Evidence from a meta-analysis. *PLOS ONE*, 10(8), e0134804. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0134804>

Longmuir, P., Colley, R., Wherley, V., & Tremblay, M. (2014). Risks and benefits of childhood physical activity. *The Lancet Diabetes & Endocrinology*, 2(11), 861-862. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-8587\(14\)70221-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2213-8587(14)70221-9)

Lubans, D. R., Richards, J., Hillman, C. H., Faulkner, G., Beauchamp, M. R., Nilsson, M., Kelly, P., Smith, J. J., Raine, L. B., & Biddle, S. J. H. (2016). Physical Activity for Cognitive and Mental Health in Youth: A Systematic Review of Mechanisms. *Pediatrics*, 138(3). <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1642>

Mantovani, A. M., Werneck, A. O., Agostinete, R. R., Lima, M. C., Codogno, J. S., Turi-Lynch, B. C., & Fernandes, R. A. (2020). Impact of physical activity during weekdays and weekends on fat mass among adults: 12-month cohort study. *Sao Paulo Medical Journal*, 138(3), 201-207. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1516-3180.2019.0465.r1.16012020>

Marques, A., Naia, A., Branquinho Cátia, & Gaspar De Matos, M. (2017). Adolescents’ eating behaviours and its relationship with family meals, body mass index and body weight perception Comportamiento alimenticio de los adolescentes y su relación con comidas familiares, índice de masa corporal y percepción del peso corporal. *Nutrición Hospitalaria*, 35(3). <https://doi.org/10.20960/nh.1540>

Mayorga Vega, D., & Viciano, J. (2017). Comparison of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity levels between physical education, school recess and after-school time in secondary school students. *Kinesiology*, 49(2), 242-251. <https://doi.org/10.26582/k.49.2.1>

Mazereel, V., Vansteelandt, K., Menne-Lothmann, C., Decoster, J., Derom, C., Thiery, E., Rutten, B. P., Jacobs, N., Van Os, J., Wichers, M., De Hert, M., Vancampfort, D., & Van Winkel, R. (2021). The complex and dynamic interplay between self-esteem, belongingness and physical activity in daily life: An experience sampling study in adolescence and young adulthood. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 21, 100413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2021.100413>

McCarthy, S. (2014). Weekly patterns, diet quality and energy balance. *Physiology & Behavior*, 134, 55-59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2014.02.046>

Megaputri, P. S., Wardani, N. L. P. E. P., Meriyani, D. A., & Widiarta, B. O. (2021). Peer Group Proximity and Self-Esteem among Bully Adolescents in Buleleng and Jembrana Regency. *NurseLine Journal*, 6(2), 130. <https://doi.org/10.19184/nlj.v6i2.19397>

Merdzhanova, E., Petrova, G., Kulina, H., & Lalova, V. (2019). A Research of adolescents physical activity and eating habits during their free time in City of Plovdiv, Bulgaria. *Journal of IMAB*, 25(4). <https://doi.org/10.5272/jimab.2019254.2713>

Minev, M., Petrova, B., Mineva, K., Petkova, M., & Strebkova, R. (2018). Self-esteem in adolescents. *Trakia Journal of Sciences*, 16(2), 114–118. <https://doi.org/10.15547/tjs.2018.02.007>

Ministry of Education C, Sports, Science and Technology: National statistics of school health (in Japanese). http://www.mext.go.jp/b_menu/toukei/chousa05/hoken/1268826.htm. Accessed 1 Apr 2017.

Moneva, J., Calunod, J., & Sumayang, J. (2020). Bullied students and their self-esteem. *International Journal of Social Science Research*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijssr.v8i2.16840>

Naeem, H., Sharif, S., Sharif, H., & Seemi, T. (2023). Self-esteem levels in school-going adolescents across the slums of Karachi, Pakistan: A cross-sectional analysis. *Frontiers in Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frcha.2023.1175826>

NCD Risk Factor Collaboration (NCD-RisC). Worldwide trends in body mass index, underweight, overweight and obesity from 1975

- to 2016: a pooled analysis of 2416 population-based measurement studies with 128.9 million children, adolescents, and adults. *Lancet*, 2017; 390 (10113): 2627-42. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(17) 32129-3.
- Ochiai, H., Shirasawa, T., Nanri, H., Nishimura, R., Nomoto, S., Hoshino, H., & Kokaze, A. (2017). Lifestyle factors associated with underweight among Japanese adolescents: a cross-sectional study. *Archives of Public Health*, 75(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13690-017-0213-9>
- Ogden, C. L., Carroll, M. D., Lawman, H. G., Fryar, C. D., Kruszon-Moran, D., Kit, B. K., & Flegal, K. M. (2016). Trends in obesity prevalence among children and adolescents in the United States, 1988-1994 through 2013-2014. *JAMA*, 315(21), 2292. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2016.6361>
- Ogihara, Y. (2016). Age Difference in self-liking in Japan: the development trajectory of self-esteem from elementary school to old age. *Letters on Evolutionary Behavioral Science*. <https://doi.org/10.5178/lebs.2016.48>
- Ogihara, Y. (2018). The development Trajectory of self-esteem in Japan: Age differences in self-liking from middle school students to the elderly. *JPN J Interpers Soc Psychol*. <https://doi.org/10.18910/70551>
- Ogihara, Y., & Kusumi, T. (2020). The developmental trajectory of self-esteem across the life span in Japan: Age differences in scores on the Rosenberg self-esteem scale from adolescence to old age. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00132>
- Orth, U., Maes, J., & Schmitt, M. (2015). Self-esteem development across the life span: A longitudinal study with a large sample from Germany. *Developmental Psychology*, 51(2), 248–259. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038481>
- Oyeyemi, A. L., Ishaku, C. M., Oyekola, J., Wakawa, H. D., Lawan, A., & Yakubu, S. (2016). Patterns and Associated Factors of Physical Activity among Adolescents in Nigeria. *PloS One*, 11(2), e0150142. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0150142>
- O'Donovan, G., Lee, I., Hamer, M., & Stamatakis, E. (2017). Association of “Weekend warrior” and other leisure time physical activity patterns with risks for all-cause, cardiovascular disease, and cancer mortality. *JAMA Internal Medicine*, 177(3), 335. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2016.8014>
- Parra, K. L., Alaofe, H. S., Ehiri, J. E., Nuño, V. L., Mazariegos, M., Garcia, B., Martinez, E., Junkins, A., & Jolly, P. (2021). Prevalence and determinants of underweight, overweight, and obesity: A cross-sectional study of Sociodemographic, dietary, and lifestyle factors among adolescent girls in Jutiapa, Guatemala. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin*, 42(4), 502-519. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03795721211019638>
- Pertiwi, N. F., & Wardani, I. Y. (2019). HARGA DIRI REMAJA DAN POLA ASUH ORANGTUA SEBAGAI FAKTOR PROTEKTIF IDE BUNUH DIRI. *Jurnal Ilmiah Permas/Jurnal Ilmiah Permas*, 9(3), 301–310. <https://doi.org/10.32583/pskm.9.3.2019.301-310>
- Peterson, N. E., Sirard, J. R., Kulbok, P. A., DeBoer, M. D., & Erickson, J. M. (2018). Sedentary behavior and physical activity of young adult university students. *Research in Nursing & Health*, 41(1), 30–38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.21845>
- Poitras, V. J., Gray, C. E., Borghese, M. M., Carson, V., Chaput, J., Janssen, I., Katzmarzyk, P. T., Pate, R. R., Gorber, S. C., Kho, M. E., Sampson, M., & Tremblay, M. S. (2016). Systematic review of the relationships between objectively measured physical activity and health indicators in school-aged children and youth. *Applied Physiology, Nutrition and Metabolism/Applied Physiology, Nutrition, and Metabolism*, 41(6 (Suppl. 3)), S197–S239. <https://doi.org/10.1139/apnm-2015-0663>
- Ploeg, K. A., Wu, B., McGavock, J., & Veugelers, P. J. (2012). Physical activity among Canadian children on school days and Nonschool days. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 9(8), 1138-1145. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.9.8.1138>
- Rawal, T., Willeboordse, M., Arora, M., Sharma, N., Nazar, G. P., Tandon, N., & Van Schayck, C. P. (2021). Prevalence of excessive weight and underweight and its associated knowledge and lifestyle behaviors among urban private school-going adolescents in New Delhi. *Nutrients*, 13(9), 3296. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13093296>
- Reddon, H., Meyre, D., & Cairney, J. (2017). Physical activity and global self-worth in a longitudinal study of children. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 49(8), 1606–1613. <https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0000000000001275>
- Rosenberg, M. (1965). Society and the adolescent self-image. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400876136>
- Rusuli, I. (2021). Which is the most appropriate parenting style for the adolescents’ self-esteem among Acehnese people? *Humanitas*, 18(1), 32. <https://doi.org/10.26555/humanitas.v18i1.15743>
- Saint-Maurice, P., Bai, Y., Vazou, S., & Welk, G. (2018). Youth physical activity patterns during school and out-of-school time. *Children*, 5(9), 118. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children5090118>
- Sani, S. H. Z., Fathirezaie, Z., Brand, S., Pühse, U., Holsboer-Trachsler, E., Gerber, M., & Talepasand, S. (2016). Physical activity and

- self-esteem: testing direct and indirect relationships associated with psychological and physical mechanisms. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, Volume 12, 2617–2625. <https://doi.org/10.2147/ndt.s116811>
- Scalas, L. F., Mars, H. W., & Nagengast, B. (2010). Longitudinal tests of competing factor structures for the Rosenberg self-esteem scale: Traits, ephemeral artifacts, and stable response styles. *Psychological Assessment*, 22(2), 366-381. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0019225>
- Scheers, T., Philippaerts, R., & Lefevre, J. (2012). Patterns of physical activity and sedentary behavior in normal-weight, overweight and obese adults, as measured with a portable armband device and an electronic diary. *Clinical Nutrition*, 31(5), 756-764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2012.04.011>
- Schmitt, D. P., & Allik, J. (2005). Simultaneous administration of the Rosenberg self-esteem scale in 53 nations: Exploring the universal and culture-specific features of global self-esteem. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 89(4), 623-642. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.89.4.623>
- Schonbeck, Y., Van Dommelen, P., HiraSing, R. A., & Van Buuren, S. (2014). Thinness in the era of obesity: trends in children and adolescents in The Netherlands since 1980. *European Journal of Public Health*, 25(2), 268–273. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/cku130>
- Seema, S., Rohilla, K. K., Kalyani, V. C., & Babbar, P. (2021). Prevalence and contributing factors for adolescent obesity in present era: Cross-sectional Study. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 10(5), 1890. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_1524_20
- Simkus, J. (2023). Stratified Random Sampling: Definition, Method & Examples. *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/stratified-random-sampling.html>
- Simmonds, M., Llewellyn, A., Owen, C. G., & Woolacott, N. (2015). Predicting adult obesity from childhood obesity: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obesity Reviews*, 17(2), 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.12334>
- Sinclair, S. J., Blais, M. A., Gansler, D. A., Sandberg, E., Bistis, K., & LoCicero, A. (2010). Psychometric properties of the Rosenberg self-esteem scale: Overall and across demographic groups living within the United States. *Evaluation & the Health Professions*, 33(1), 56-80. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163278709356187>
- Singh, J. K., Acharya, D., Rani, D., Gautam, S., Bajgain, K. T., Bajgain, B. B., Park, J., Yoo, S., Poder, T. G., Lewin, A., & Lee, K. (2021). Underweight and associated factors among teenage adolescent girls in resource-poor settings: a cross-sectional study. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy*, Volume 14, 9–19. <https://doi.org/10.2147/rmhp.s280499>
- Siwarom, S., Pirojsakul, K., Aekplakorn, W., Paksi, W., Kessomboon, P., Neelapaichit, N., Chariyalertsak, S., Assanangkornchai, S., & Taneepanichskul, S. (2021). Waist-to-Height ratio is a good predictor of metabolic syndrome in adolescents: a report from the Thai National Health Examination Survey V, 2014. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Public Health*, 34(1), 36–43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10105395211046474>
- Smith, L., Hamer, M., Ucci, M., Marmot, A., Gardner, B., Sawyer, A., Wardle, J., & Fisher, A. (2015). Weekday and weekend patterns of objectively measured sitting, standing, and stepping in a sample of office-based workers: The active buildings study. *BMC Public Health*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-014-1338-1>
- Twenge, J. M., Miller, J. D., & Campbell, W. K. (2014). The narcissism epidemic: Commentary on Modernity and narcissistic personality disorder. *Personality Disorders*, 5(2), 227–229. <https://doi.org/10.1037/per0000008>
- Uchoa, F. N., Andrade, J. H., Lustosa, R. P., & Daniele, T. M. (2019). Motricidade. Impact of physical activity on the Body Mass Index and self-esteem of adolescents. DOI: 10.6063/motricidade.19472
- Valdés, S., García-Torres, F., Maldonado-Araque, C., Goday, A., Calle-Pascual, A., Soriguer, F., Castaño, L., Catalá, M., Gomis, R., & Rojo-Martínez, G. (2014). Prevalencia de obesidad, diabetes mellitus y otros factores de riesgo cardiovascular en Andalucía. Comparación con datos de prevalencia nacionales. *Estudio Di@bet.es*. *Revista Española De Cardiología/Revista Española De Cardiología*, 67(6), 442–448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.recesp.2013.09.031>
- Varma, V. R., Dey, D., Leroux, A., Di, J., Urbanek, J., Xiao, L., & Zipunnikov, V. (2017). Re-evaluating the effect of age on physical activity over the lifespan. *Preventive Medicine*, 101, 102–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2017.05.030>
- Vedøy, I. B., Skulberg, K. R., Anderssen, S. A., Tjomsland, H. E., & Thurston, M. (2021). Physical activity and academic achievement among Norwegian adolescents: Findings from a longitudinal study. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 21, 101312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2021.101312>
- Viciano, J., Mayorga-Vega, D., & Martínez-Baena, A. (2016). Moderate-to-Vigorous physical activity levels in physical education, school recess, and after-school time: Influence of gender, age, and weight status. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 13(10), 1117-1123. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2015-0537>
- Voelker, D. K., Reel, J. J., & Greenleaf, C. (2015). Weight status and body image perceptions in adolescents: current perspectives.

Adolescent Health, Medicine, and Therapeutics, 149. <https://doi.org/10.2147/ahmt.s68344>

Wang, D., Wang, D., & Chen, W. (2022). The relationship between adolescents' resilience and their malevolent creative behaviors. *Acta Psychologica Sinica*, 54(2), 154–167. <https://doi.org/10.3724/sp.j.1041.2022.00154>

Warburton, D. E. R., & Bredin, S. S. D. (2017). Health benefits of physical activity. *Current Opinion in Cardiology/Current Opinion in Cardiology*, With Evaluated MEDLINE, 32(5), 541–556. <https://doi.org/10.1097/hco.0000000000000437>

Watson, A., Elliott, J., & Mehta, K. (2015). Perceived barriers and facilitators to participation in physical activity during the school lunch break for girls aged 12–13 years. *European Physical Education Review*, 21(2), 257–271. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356336x14567545>

Whiteman, H. (2017, August 26). Endorphin release differs by exercise intensity, study finds. *Medical News Today*. <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/319157>

Whiting, E. F., Hinton, A. E., & Jensen, B. (2022). Loving lunch in junior high: Lunchtime activities and a sense of belonging in school. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 50(7), 2973–2992. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcop.22809>

World Health Organization. (2019). Global Strategy on Diet, Physical Activity and Health. https://www.who.int/dietphysicalactivity/factsheet_young_people/en/

World Health Organization. (2020). Body Mass Index - BMI.

World Health Organization. (2023). Obesity and Overweight. <https://www.who.int/health-topics/obesity>

World Health Organization. (2023). Malnutrition. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/malnutrition>

World Health Organization: WHO. (2016). Obesity and overweight. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>

Yan Yan et al. (2021). Rosenberg self-esteem score in Chinese high school students and college students.

Yang, J., Xu, X., Chen, Y., Shi, Z., & Han, S. (2016). Trait self-esteem and neural activities related to self-evaluation and social feedback. *Scientific Reports*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep20274>

Yang, L., Bovet, P., Ma, C., Zhao, M., Liang, Y., & Xi, B. (2018). Prevalence of underweight and overweight among young adolescents aged 12–15 years in 58 low-income and middle-income countries. *Pediatric Obesity*, 14(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijpo.12468>

Yu, J., Putnick, D. L., Hendricks, C., & Bornstein, M. H. (2019). Long-Term effects of parenting and adolescent Self-Competence for the development of optimism and neuroticism. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 48(8), 1544–1554. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-018-0980-9>

Zayed, K., Al-Busafi, M., & Hadabi, B. A. (2016). Gender differences in self-esteem and its relationship with body mass index among Omani adolescents. *Sultan Qaboos University House of Expertise*. <https://squ.elsevierpure.com/en/publications/gender-differences-in-self-esteem-and-its-relationship-with-body--2>

Zimmermann-Sloutskis, D., Wanner, M., Zimmermann, E., & Martin, B. W. (2010). Physical activity levels and determinants of change in young adults: a longitudinal panel study. *the International Journal of Behavioural Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-7-2>

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